

9

Decoding and Mapping Cultural Geography of Kodungallur

**Jameelathu. K. A.,
Assistant Professor,
MES Asmabi College,
P. Vemballur, Kodungallur,
Kerala, India.**

***Abstract:** Cultural Geography assimilates the peculiarities of a place, its people and its general attitude. It evaluates a place critically and investigates in the compositions of its traces. It helps in finding out the peculiarity of or the unique nature of a place and again moving onto investigate how the stages are repeated or reinforced in that particular cultural geography. It again moves on to investigate the popularity of the traces and its persuasiveness. Sometimes environmental determinism also is a key factor in determining the uniqueness of a particular geographical area. Places and its geographical position are central to understand the nature of the community. It is a key factor in positioning human identity and cultural geography. 'Sense of place' or sense of belonging to one place creates an emotional affinity among the people living in a particular geographical area. This sense of belonging causes sprouting up of several cults or cultural groups having common values and customised features that may contribute to their uniqueness and create specific cultural geography.*

Keywords: Determinism, Cult, Positioning, Sense of Place, Kodungallur, Geography, Culture

The complex combination of culture and context results in creating multiple cultural geographies within a particular geographical division. History of a particular place also contributes to create a cultural uniqueness. History of a place, if it has a generous leaning, persuades the human community to follow the same virtue; and if it has a stigma, it persuades the human community to rectify it and the latent the emotional urge to be virtuous sometimes mark the strong cultural geography of a geographical area. The nature of the human community and the environment they are destined to have, are sometimes tested to evaluate the unique cultural geography of a place. The identification with certain peculiar or specific environmental distinctions brings about a plurality which attains a permanent status.

Even the existence of non-human species, its adaptation and survival within an area influences its cultural geography. As a result cultural difference sometimes becomes an effect of differences in environment. Or in other words environment determines a place's culture. Frequency of natural disasters like earthquakes, landslides and tempests measures the level of civilization or sophistication of an area. Many geographers undertaking researches have analysed a very close relationship between environment and culture of a geographical area. They found out that the pleasant condition of an area is mostly influenced by a moderate climate. This pleasant condition naturally brought about a rich cultural tradition and humanity. It is 'landscape culture' Unpleasant environment brings about an 'in-house culture' which is totally different from landscape culture.

Tracing the cultural landscape is an important element in determining cultural geography of a place. Natural landscape and cultural landscape are subjected to transformation at the hands of man. A man is the chief determinant of both these landscapes.

Wherever a more harmonious relationship between man and nature can be ascertained, a rich cultural geography can be found. A romantic tradition naturally produces a rich cultural geography. The historical progression of a place also determines its cultural geography. The rural and pastoral beauty of a place brings about landscape aesthetics.

Cultural geography investigates both the material entities of culture and mental association that a place a thing or a process had for its people. A place has much significance as man is rooted in it and he himself associates the place with many of his emotional identifications as to say, a birth place, ancestors' origin, origin of ideas, events, miracles, historical relevance, place of important institutions, root place of ancient trade and commerce etc. It might be a place where a community experienced specific struggle in creation of values and meanings and origin of certain norms. Sometimes it may have some symbolic significance also like a place where unprecedented activities take place. Some unexpected events, malignant and beneficial also create a cultural geography.

A place can be a text having multitudinous noteworthiness. As a literary text has several interpretations and evaluations, place also have different interpretations and evaluations. It too does have a heroic vigour and villainous manifestation just as the different level readings of a text. This morphological identification of a place conceptualises cultural geography. So it is a root place of so many social groups having different morphological identities. There are so many texts associated with cultural geography. A Cultural geographer's method is to identify these morphological identities analysing the nature and behaviour of these social groups and interpreting these texts accordingly.

Kodungallur plays a key role in the cultural geography of Kerala. Unity in the diverse geography marks Kodungallur's identity. The area nurtures solidarity even if it has different morphological identities inside it. The community acknowledges this plurality and diversity and imbibes its differences as it nurtures inclusion. History calls it Muziris as Greek preferred it so and it was a legendary port in international trade during the ancient days.

The area is culturally important for three most important religious groups Hinduism, Islam and Christianity. Geographically it situates at the South Western part of Thrissur district on the bank of river Periyar on the Malabar Coast. The Western limit of this place is Arabian sea. It is a very versatile geographical area with backwaters. Many streams brooks, ponds, lakes and even small hills mark the geographical diversity of this place. Just as water and soil are seen in different volumes as shapes, people here philosophically imbibes the unity of content in different matters. Kodungallur was the capital city of Cheraman Perumal dynasty.

It owns a lot many ancient names like Vanchi, Muchari, Muziris, Shingly, Mahodayapuram, Makothai, Cranganore and Kodilingapuram. It has different dimensional historical significances. Pleany has recorded it as premium Emporium Indiac, i.e one of the most important ports. In Ramayana Sugriva refers it as Muchari Pattanam. Kulashegharas report it as Mahodayapuram.

It was an ancient port in the first century BC and it facilitated the entry of diverse religions in the guise of trade. Cargo vessels from several parts of the world used to drop anchor at the port of Muziris. The fame of port reached various parts of the world who decided to connect through trade and the plurality of the people here might have welcomed missionaries also. So since 15th

century Muziris came under the influence of foreign powers like Portuguese Dutch and British. The socio cultural history of Kodungallur says a lot about its adaptability and plurality. The culture of Kodungallur imbibed hybridization and as different from other parts of Kerala, Kodungallur has developed its own unique culture.

It can be a symbol for the ideals which are upheld by the preface of Indian constitution. Fraternity, secularism, socialism, democracy, plurality etc can be embodied in the cultural geography of Kodungallur. Kodungallur is of great importance to all major sections of religion like Christianity Hinduism and Islam and to some minor sections like Judaism. And it its geography contains the oldest of churches and mosques namely St Thomas Church and Cherman Juma Masjid. And the great Kodungallur Bhagavathi temple was built during the reign of Chera King Cheran Senguttuvan. The festivals in Kodungallur temple show the solidarity of the religion the irrespective of its caste distinctions.

St Thomas Church is the first Christian Church in India established by Saint Thomas who landed in Kodungallur in 52 AD. He is also believed to have been the architect of churches in Kottakkavu, Palayur, Kollam, Kokkamangalam, Niranam and Nilackal. Cheraman Juma Masjid follows the architectural style of Hindu temples as it was built in 629 AD by Malik Binn Dheenar. This mosque is originally constructed of wood but later renovated using concrete minarets, but the interiors remained wooden. This mosque is considered to be the oldest in India and the second oldest to offer Juma prayers in the world. People visit this mosque and church irrespective of their religion.

As this was the port facilitated the entry of many tradesmen from different parts of the world Portuguese build a fort in 1523 AD.

This fort is known as Kottapuram fort. Dutch took possession of it in 1661 and later it came under Tipu Sultan. Tipu Sultan is believed to have destroyed it but the remains of the fort are known as Tipu's fort, the oldest Shiva temple in South India, Thiruvanchikulam Mahadeva temple is an important temple of historical significance and it hosts the famous Anayottam or elephant race as the part of annual temple festival.

Judaism also has significant landmark here as Paravur synagogue is an important centre of Kodungallur heritage. This mixture of religions and festivals associated with them brought a feeling of oneness and thereby helped in nurturing a common culture and a feeling of solidarity among the people of this region. As from centuries before this area received different types of people mixed with different types of cultures it has imbibed most of its generous nature as peace and welcoming faces invites trade and commerce. Naturally it became a gateway to so many religions also. And this particular uniqueness of this particular area promoted a rich culture and adaptability among the people of this particular area. The people here know how to deal with people from different areas naturally it has various representations from the past and it invites archaeologists' interests.

As Kerala itself is known as god's own country, Kodungallur, the central part of Kerala can be regarded as the abode of God. It is a real model to the diverse culture of India to showcase its unity in diversity. Traces when examined, vividly shows the existence of a cosmopolitan community in and around Kodungallur. Literature and culture gets enriched in an atmosphere of peace and love. So the land gave birth to so many literary men and artists. The setting of backwaters also helps in creating a literary atmosphere. The cultural landscape of Kodungallur can be read of as a text symbolising the cultural unity which encompasses cultural

diversity. Festivals which are celebrated in different religious institutions like churches, mosques and temples are also texts that can be read as symbols of cultural unity inclusive of cultural diversity.

Environmental determinism is another text which unifies the diverse tastes into one. As it is a land of backwaters and its proximity to Arabian Seashore, it has to face unpredictable tides and the consequences of it. The people are frequently hit at their conscience about the oneness of fate of human beings notwithstanding man made distinctions on the basis of caste, colour, class etc. Year wise renewal of troubles caused by monsoon enrooted a cultural identification that in turn created a literary leaning cementing spiritual and philosophical acceptance of helplessness of human beings in the face of calamities.

"Culture is not a residual category, the surface variation left unaccounted for by more powerful economic analyses; it is a very medium through which social change is experienced contested and constituted" (Cosgrove and Jackson 1987:95)

From ancient times itself Kodungallur has proved its economic stability as it has been a Trade centre from time immemorial. The strength and economic stability of Kodungallur originated from its readiness to adapt to different cultural racial and religious sections has understood that peace and prosperity is brought forth with patience and mixing up. When Portuguese, Dutch, Arabian and English merchants and missionaries touched this port, they could breathe in an amiable wind. Cultural life does not take place in hostile conditions. The nature of the people of the society is an important factor in improving cultural geography.

And so the people of Kodungallur imbibed the significance of accepting and merging with the given atmosphere so as to improve

themselves. They gave importance to the nature and culture of the people who came with different intentions. Muziris always opened the doors to diversity and prosperity and the result is visible in its cultural landscape and cultural background. The port acted as the gateway to the cultural life of Kodungallur. The intermixture of land and water geographically pointed at the need for diversity and the need for unification of the Identities in the diversity. People of Kodungallur always followed certain traditions and customs which are in accordance with the principles followed by Indian constitution or Gandhiji's principle of sarvamathasambhava. We can see willful corporation and voluntary contribution to the different customs and traditions and festivals associated with religions and whole hearted participation from all sections of society is assured as a unique 'Kodungallur story' irrespective of specific religions.

Naturally the cultural geography of Kodungallur is a fertile soil to literary activities and literary men. Only a peaceful atmosphere with certain element related difficulties can unify polycentric voice into a single soul. When we make an archetypal enquiry into the literary works of the area we can find a recurring emotion of oneness connecting all the literary works. Place is very important as in Kodungallur the communities and the people here define certain values and attach them with their life and inter relationships. In every literary works of this particular geographical area we can find these values expressed notwithstanding the different stories they explore. The cultural meanings that the people here give to their homeland are linked with the three monuments which anchor this cultural geography and mould it to raise it to the sky top. The all-round space of this cultural geographical area is defined by the values inscribed on

these cultural monuments each of which has a cultural space of its own.

Place and space of Kodungallur are significant in the way that the values upheld by this region is not shared in the same way by any sections of society anywhere in the world but the people here are so intimate and emotive to these values as it is their own creation. It can be applied to any space and is always significant. The space, Kodungallur spreads to the world is open and detached. Kodungallur roots its people geographically, socially and culturally. It always takes pride in its historical 'traces'. The traces of history of monuments located in Kodungallur say about the cultural centre of the place and its space is widely discussed because of this centrality. This centrality actually intensifies the prominence of its space and adds core meaning to it by making it core text on which different dimensional meanings can be added. It gets relevant media space also. Researches on print news and online news show that even when the state has undergone severe political and economic crises, the area was not much affected because of this sense of solidarity of the people here.

When literary texts are investigated a common linear structure can be seen. Cultural values and anthropogeography, cultural practices and social organisations, indigenous knowledge and 'mythified' habits, all lie dormant and common under these superficially different texts. That is to say, several similar texts with personal modifications can be seen and read under these different texts. The diverse texts' expressions of cultures like religions and dialectical variations of Malayalam expressed in Kodungallur, bear witness to its divine cultural landscape inside God's own country. It is impregnated with rituals and customs though different, are cosmopolitan and secular. Though paddy fields and arable lands have metamorphosed into buildings and structures, though

common cradle of the joint family and ancestral homes are abated into nuclear flats devoid of soil and ponds, Kodungallur has tried to perpetuate the 'feel good' happy face amongst the cultural struggle and imposition of social control through political means.

The area never witnesses a cultural hegemony or cultural imperialism. Differences are assimilated as 'God given' individual differences in a single family. Naturally this cultural landscape made use of its ancient international priority to develop a culture called Muziris Culture and is attracting Eco-tourism past decades. Resultant cultural diffusion is an optimistic trait. Its landmass has been formed through a sequence of transgressions and regressions of the sea over a million of years. Just as the soil which is softened through these, the culture of this area is moulded by many 'gives and takes'. The intellectual terrain or the territory of thought of this area moves in through its past glory which it struggles to retain as its egalitarian way is an intelligent diplomacy to maintain peace and harmony, thereby ensuring prosperity. Iconic texts portraying these relations are written by masters who were also its progeny. Centring of historical and religious institutions in and around Kodungallur is a key factor for its prominence and peace. Locating these material artefacts in this cultural region, the area resisted the entry of fanaticism in many forms, like politics, religion and ethnicity. The area is a democratic place typically rural and traditional with particular ways of life. The values, beliefs dialectal variations of language, meaning and practices of this area show their particular way of life.

Deciphering the meanings of various 'texts' like festivals, literary endeavours, number of writers, processions(various), marriage, etc., the importance of this cultural geography is significantly improving as days pass by. A textual reading of this shows that people here are reluctant to move away from this euphoria of

having the special cultural identity of values and virtues. Temple related, mosque related and church related festivals, all have similar meanings and are attended by all people irrespective of class, caste and religion. Numbers of literary men are many under this cultural geography. All the processions are more secular than sectional. Literary works are more philosophical and secular and adaptive. Community functions related to marriages and deaths are more accommodative and are attended by all. Some rituals attached with marriage ceremony are even similar for all religions.

Certain specific features are attached with places and their culture. The thought of Kodungallur brings about a cultural uniqueness incomparable with any other areas of Kerala's cultural geography. This common idea overpowers other considerations when one visits this place. The fixed identity of cosmopolitan and adaptive secular nature maps out the Interconnections of its cultural geography with others. The evaluation of a place and its cultural geography is more a theoretical and narrative. This is an empirical research on Kodungallur and it requires field visits and surveys across different sites. This is not a comprehensive analysis, but only a glimpse into the cultural geography of Kodungallur. Case studies and questionnaires may be needed for further analysis.

Works Cited

Agnew, John. "The Territorial Trap: The Geographical Assumptions of International Relations Theory". *Review of International Political Economy*, vol.1, 1994. pp. 53-80.

Aitken, Stuart. C and Gill Valentine. *Approaches to Human Geography: Philosophies, Theories, People and Practices*. SAGE Publications, 2006.

Anderson, Benedict. *Imagined Communities: Reflections on the Origin and Spread of Nationalism*. Verso, 2006.

Menon, A. Sreedhara. *Kodungallur: The City of Temples*. Government of Kerala, Department of Archaeology, 2004.

Narayanan, MGS. *Kodungallur: Socio-Cultural Artifacts of a Medieval Port City*. National Bookstall, 2001.